

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component

PLCy2 Solution Substrate Synthesis – C8CF3C

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Introduction

1-Phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2 (PLC γ 2, PLCG2) is an enzyme that converts PIP2 (phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate, PtdIns(4,5)P2, PI(4,5)P2) into IP3 (1D-myo-inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate) and diacylglycerol (DAG). PLC γ 2 is mainly expressed in immune cells and microglia, but only sparsely expressed in other brain cells such as astrocytes and oligodendrocytes.[1] A rare coding variant in PLC γ 2, Pro522Arg (P522R), was identified from an Alzheimer's disease genome-wide association study (GWAS)[2] and replicated in various populations.[3,4,5] This mutation was found to confer a protective effect where patients who carried this P522R mutation exhibited a slower rate of cognitive decline than patients who did not.[2] While the exact mechanism of this protective effect of the P522R PLC γ 2 mutant is not fully understood, this mutation does induce a slight increase in enzymatic activity.[1] Therefore, pharmacological intervention that increases the wild-type PLCG2's activity may provide a therapeutic strategy to lessen the cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease patients.

At the time of writing, published literature described only two molecules that activate phospholipase C (PLC) enzymes in vitro, U73122 (1-(6-((17 β -3-methoxyestra-1,3,5(10)-trien-17-yl)amino)hexyl)-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione) [7] and m-3M3FBS (2,4,6-trimethyl-N-(meta-3-trifluoromethyl-phenyl)-benzenesulfonamide) [8]. U73122 has been shown to activate PLC β and PLC γ family members in vitro [7], but it was originally identified as an inhibitor of PLCs.[9] In fact, U73122 was extensively used as the prototypical inhibitor of PLC enzymes in cell culture.[10,11,12,13,14] However, more recently U73122 has also been shown to affect numerous other cellular proteins including phospholipase D [15], 5-lipoxygenase [16], calcium channels [17], potassium channels [18], telomerase [19], histamine H1 receptor [20], and sarco/endoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺-ATPase.[21] This complete lack of specificity is not surprising as the maleimide in U73122 can react with the thiol present in cysteine residues. Therefore, it is highly likely that U73122 non-specifically reacts with exposed cysteines on numerous proteins within a cell. This lack of specificity and high reactivity make U73122 a poor option to base a medicinal chemistry campaign with the goal of developing selective PLC γ 2 activators.

m-3M3FBS was originally identified from a screen of compounds that enhanced superoxide-generating activity in human neutrophils [8]. This activity was proposed to be caused by the direct activation of PLCs.[8] Supporting this proposition, several labs have shown that one downstream signaling effect of PLC activation—intracellular calcium release—was observed in various cell types treated with m-3M3FBS.[22,23,24,25,26] However, the potency and specificity of PLC activation of m-3M3FBS has been called into question, as there are reports that intracellular calcium release occurs before any PLC activity is detected,[27] and that m-3M3FBS effects the inward and outward flow of ions in a PLC-independent manner possibly through the direct inhibition of delayed rectifier potassium channels.[28] Additionally,

Figure 1. Chemical structures of putative literature reported PLC γ 2 activators U73122 and m-3M3FBS.

m-3M3FBS has been shown to be cytotoxic in some cell lines.[23,24,25] Currently, it is unclear if m-3M3FBS exerts its activity primarily through PLC activation and if it does, whether a derivative could be identified that is selective for PLC γ 2.

As no selective small molecule activators of PLC γ 2 are currently known, there is a clear need to identify such an activator to determine whether the pharmacological activation of PLC γ 2 is a viable therapeutic strategy to treat Alzheimer's disease. Fortunately, there are enzymatic assays that have already been developed that are amenable for high-throughput screening (HTS).[29,30] These assays were primarily developed to identify inhibitors of PLC enzymes,[31] but these assays and substrates can be readily modified to screen for PLC γ 2 activators. These assays can be broadly classified into two groups. The first utilizes a water soluble substrate epitomized by WH-15 that measures the catalytic activity of PLC enzymes in solution,[29] while the second uses a hydrophobic substrate such as XY-69 that imbeds in a micelle or liposome to measure the activity of PLC enzymes at a surface interface that better mimics the natural membrane-bound substrate PIP2 [30].

In this resource document, we detail the synthesis of a fluorimetric PLC γ 2 substrate that is amenable to measuring PLC γ 2's solution, non-membrane associated catalytic activity.

Synthesis

Multi-gram synthesis of intermediate **5** was completed by scientists at Cayman Chemical Company in Ann Arbor, MI. This was done by following exactly or slightly modified versions of the procedures of Huang et al. [31] and references therein, with one major exception: intermediate **2** was synthesized in a new way (**Scheme 1**), which was inspired by the work of Bjørsvik et al. [32]. Thus, 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (**1**) was treated with 2.5 eq of NaH to generate a dianion, whose 3-position phenoxide more readily reacted than the 4-position phenoxide with the electrophile, 1-iodooctane. This procedure was more amenable to multi-gram scale synthesis of **2** than the published procedure, and it decreased the overall step count. Once intermediate **5** was in hand, researchers at Purdue University conjugated the fluorescent reporter 7-amino-4-trifluoromethyl-coumarin (**3**) to **5** via a carbamate linkage to give **6**, executed global deprotection of **6** using TMSBr, and finally purified by reversed phase chromatography to furnish the substrate C8CF3C (**7**) in tris•NEt₃ salt form (**Scheme 2**).

Scheme 1. Novel synthesis of intermediate **2**.

Scheme 2. Completion of substrate **7**.

Chemistry General Procedures:

Reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources and used without further purification, except where indicated. Widely practiced methods were followed to conduct, analyze, and purify reactions, including techniques for exclusion of moisture and oxygen where appropriate. 4 Å molecular sieves were prepared for use by drying at $110\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ overnight, and were cooled to rt under N_2 atmosphere

immediately prior to use. TMSBr was distilled (bp 79 °C) at atmospheric pressure under N₂ atmosphere. NMR data were collected on 400 MHz JEOL or 500 MHz Bruker instruments. For ¹H NMR, chemical shifts in ppm relative to the residual solvent peak, multiplicities, coupling constants in Hertz, and numbers of protons are indicated. For ¹³C NMR, chemical shifts in ppm relative to the residual solvent peak are indicated. For ¹⁹F and ³¹P NMR, chemical shifts in ppm relative to an external standard are indicated. Analytical TLC was performed on F254 silica gel plates, and 254 nm UV light, I₂ staining, and/or 10% H₂SO₄ staining were used for visualization. NP flash chromatography was performed on a Teledyne-ISCO NextGen300 instrument using prepacked silica gel columns available from Teledyne-ISCO, or in glass columns using loose SilicaFlash F60 silica gel. RP flash chromatography was performed on a Teledyne-ISCO NextGen300 instrument using prepacked C18-derivatized silica gel columns available from Teledyne-ISCO. Analytical LC-MS data were obtained on (1) a Waters ACQUITY UPLC equipped with Waters ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 column (1.7 μm, 50 mm x 2.1 mm), TUV dual-wavelength detector, and SQD2 mass detector (ESI), or (2) an Agilent 1200 HPLC stack equipped with Agilent Zorbax SB-C8 column (5 μm, 50 mm x 2.1 mm) or Waters Atlantis T3 C18 column (3 μm, 50 mm x 3.0 mm), 1100 Diode Array Detector G1315B, and 6130A Quadrupole mass detector (ESI and APCI). High-resolution mass spectra were obtained on Agilent 6550 Q-TOF or Thermo Q Exactive instruments.

Intermediate 2

A solution of 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (**1**, 3.00 g, 21.7 mmol) in DMF (10 mL) was added dropwise to a 0 °C solution of 1-iodooctane (3.65 g, 15.2 mmol) in DMF (20 mL) and the reaction was stirred for 30 min. Then, a solution of a 60% oil dispersion of NaH (2.15 g, 53.8 mmol) in THF (20 mL) was added dropwise and the reaction was allowed to slowly warm to rt while stirring for 48 h. The reaction was then warmed to 50 °C with stirring for 3 h upon which it was quenched with H₂O (50 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (3 x 50 mL). The combined organic phases were washed with brine (50 mL) and concentrated to give an oily residue. The residue was purified by flash LC on a silica gel column, eluting with 97:3 to 92:8 heptane:EtOAc gradient to provide **2** (1.20 g, 29%) as a colorless oil.

TLC R_f = 0.70 (80:20 heptane:EtOAc)

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ 9.80 (s, 1H), 7.4 – 7.4 (m, 2H), 7.02 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 1H), 6.28 (s, 1H), 4.10 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 2H), 1.9 – 1.8 (m, 2H), 1.5 – 1.4 (m, 2H), 1.4 – 1.2 (m, 8H), 0.87 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H)

¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) δ 191.1, 151.9, 146.6, 129.9, 127.4, 114.4, 109.6, 69.3, 31.9, 29.4, 29.3, 29.1, 26.0, 22.7, 14.2

ESI-HRMS for [M+H]⁺ C₁₅H₂₃O₃: calcd 251.1647, found 251.1639

Intermediate 5

Preparation of **5** followed exactly or slightly modified versions of the procedures of Huang et al. [31] and references therein, with the major exception noted above. The characterization data were consistent with the published data.

TLC R_f = 0.33 (50:50 hexanes:acetone)

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ 7.3 – 7.2 (m, 26H), 6.94 (s, 1H), 6.80 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 5.3 – 5.2 (m, 2H), 5.2 – 4.9 (m, 9H), 4.7 – 4.6 (m, 6H), 4.5 – 4.5 (m, 1H), 4.4 – 4.2 (m, 4H), 4.2 – 4.1 (m, 1H), 4.0 – 3.9 (m, 2H), 3.6 – 3.5 (m, 1H), 3.4 – 3.3 (m, 4H), 3.26 (s, 2H), 3.17 (s, 3H), 2.15 (s, 1H), 1.8 – 1.7 (m, 2H), 1.4 – 1.3 (m, 2H), 1.3 – 1.2 (m, 8H), 0.85 (t, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 3H)

³¹P NMR (CDCl₃, 162 MHz) δ -0.62, -0.64, -6.01, -6.15

ESI-HRMS for [M+H]⁺ C₆₂H₈₀O₂₀P₃: calcd 1237.4456, found 1237.4458

Intermediate 6

Preparation of isocyanate **4** followed a modified version of a procedure from Kim et al.[33] 7-Amino-4-trifluoromethyl-coumarin (**3**, 58 mg, 0.253 mmol) was suspended in anhydrous dichloroethane (5 mL). NEt_3 (69 μL , 0.495 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred at rt for ~15 min. Triphosgene (74 mg, 0.249 mmol) was then added. The reaction mixture was heated to 90 °C for 1 hr and became a solution. Complete conversion of **3** to **4** was confirmed by quenching an aliquot with MeOH to form the methyl carbamate of **3** and then checking TLC or LC-MS. The reaction mixture was cooled to rt and concentrated in vacuo to yield crude **4** as a yellowish white semisolid.

To crude **4** was added anhydrous DCM (1 mL) and stirring was initiated to produce a yellow solution. Activated 4 Å molecular sieves were added, followed by dropwise addition of a solution of intermediate **5** (206 mg, 94.05% purity, 0.157 mmol) in anhydrous DCM (1 mL), and finally a rinse of anhydrous DCM (1 mL) from the vial that contained **5**. Triethylamine (69 μL , 0.495 mmol) was then added, followed by DMAP (4 mg, 0.033 mmol). The bright yellow solution was allowed to stir at rt for ~30 min with TLC or LC-MS monitoring. When **5** was no longer detected, the reaction mixture was quenched by addition of aqueous saturated NH_4Cl solution (5 mL). The organic layer was removed and the aqueous solution was extracted with DCM (2 x 5 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified the same day by flash LC on a 12-g silica gel column, eluting with 90:10 to 50:50 hexanes:acetone gradient to provide **6** (200 mg, 86%) as a white solid.

TLC R_f = 0.45 (50:50 hexanes:acetone)

^1H NMR (DMSO-d_6 , 500 MHz) δ 10.47 (s, 1H), 7.70 – 7.63 (m, 2H), 7.49 (dd, J = 8.9, 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.38 – 7.20 (m, 27H), 7.00 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 6.88 (s, 1H), 5.23 (t, J = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 5.17 (s, 2H), 5.13 – 4.95 (m, 8H), 4.85 – 4.62 (m, 6H), 4.62 – 4.49 (m, 2H), 4.46 – 4.25 (m, 2H), 4.04 – 3.95 (m, 4H), 3.31 (s, 3H), 3.25 (d, J = 17.2 Hz, 2H), 3.21 – 3.14 (m, 5H), 1.65 (h, J = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 1.39 – 1.30 (m, 2H), 1.22 – 1.15 (m, 7H), 0.80 (t, J = 6.9 Hz, 3H)

QTOF-HRMS for $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ $\text{C}_{73}\text{H}_{84}\text{F}_3\text{NO}_{23}\text{P}_3$: calcd 1492.4586, found 1492.4594

C8CF3C tris• NEt_3 salt (**7**)

Intermediate **6** (200 mg, 0.134 mmol) was dissolved with stirring in anhydrous DCM (2 mL) to give a faint yellow solution. The solution was cooled to ~5 °C in an ice-water bath, and then freshly distilled TMSBr (2.0 mL) was added dropwise. The mixture was stirred for 15 min in the ice-water bath, and then it was removed from the bath and allowed to warm to rt for 45 min. The reaction progress was followed by LC-MS and it showed complete disappearance of intermediate **6**. The reaction mixture appeared as a yellow solution at this time. The mixture was concentrated in vacuo and the resulting yellow oil was dried under high vacuum for 1.5 hrs.

To the residue was added MeOH (2 mL), and the resulting solution was stirred at rt for 1 h. The solution was concentrated in vacuo and the resulting yellow oil was dried under high-vacuum for 1 h. Aqueous 1.0 M pH 8.5 TEAB buffer (1.5 mL) was added to the residue and it was stirred to give a clear yellow solution. The solution was subjected to flash LC on a 50-g C18 column using a gradient of 95:5 $\text{H}_2\text{O}:\text{ACN}$ and MeOH to give **7** (115 mg, 71%) as a barely yellow white solid. [Note: different preparations gave varying ratios of NEt_3 per substrate molecule; it was typically 3 ± 0.5 NEt_3 per substrate molecule. The NMR data below correspond to 3.5 NEt_3 per substrate molecule.]

TLC R_f = 0.00 (50:50 hexanes:acetone)

^1H NMR (CD_3OD , 500 MHz) δ 7.75 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.66 – 7.61 (m, 1H), 7.59 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 7.39 (dd, J = 8.8, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.04 (s, 1H), 6.91 (dd, J = 8.3, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 6.71 (s, 1H), 5.14 (s, 2H), 4.39 (q, J = 9.0

Hz, 1H), 4.34 (t, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H), 4.17 – 4.09 (m, 1H), 4.06 – 3.95 (m, 4H), 3.58 (dd, *J* = 9.6, 2.7 Hz, 1H), 3.10 (q, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 21H), 1.79 (p, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2H), 1.45 (p, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 2H), 1.39 – 1.22 (m, 39H), 0.87 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H)

¹⁹F NMR (CD₃OD, 470 MHz) δ -67.58

³¹P NMR (CD₃OD, 202 MHz) δ 3.69, 2.71, -4.13

QTOF-HRMS for [M-H]⁻ C₃₂H₄₀F₃NO₂₀P₃: calcd 908.1309, found 908.1328

HPLC purity 97.56% (λ = 254 nm, see method in SI)

Supporting Information

Supporting information is provided within this document, and contains NMR and LC-MS data.

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Supporting Information

Compound 2

Compound 12 C8

Item #

Batch #

File Name	\\sulfur\private\nmrdata\JEOL_2022\KS2224-4\KS2224-4 PROTON 26-Apr-2022-1-1.jdf		
Date	26 Apr 2022 09:37:35	Nucleus	1H
Solvent	CHLOROFORM-d	Frequency (MHz)	399.5822
Temperature (degree C)	20.300	Number of Transients	16
		Origin	JEOL ECZ400S Sc v601

^1H NMR (CHLOROFORM-d, 400 MHz) δ 9.80 (s, 1H), 7.4-7.4 (m, 2H), 7.02 (d, 1H, $J=8.7$ Hz), 6.28 (s, 1H), 4.10 (t, 2H, $J=6.6$ Hz), 1.8-1.9 (m, 2H), 1.4-1.5 (m, 2H), 1.2-1.4 (m, 8H), 0.87 (t, 3H, $J=6.7$ Hz)

Compound 2

Compound 12 C8

Item #

Batch #

File Name	\\sulfur\private\nmrdata\JEOL_2022\KS2224-4\KS2224-4 CARBON 26-Apr-2022-1-1.jdf				
Date	26 Apr 2022 09:51:41	Nucleus	13C	Frequency (MHz)	100.4750
Solvent	CHLOROFORM-d	Number of Transients	256	Origin	JEOL ECZ400S Sc v601
Temperature (degree C)	20.400				

^{13}C NMR (CHLOROFORM-d, 100 MHz) δ 191.1, 151.9, 146.6, 129.9, 127.4, 114.4, 109.6, 69.3, 31.9, 29.4, 29.3, 29.1, 26.0, 22.7, 14.2

Compound 5

WH15 Compd 15 C8

Item #

Batch #

File Name	\\sulfur\private\nmrdata\JEOL_2021\KS-1987-142\KS-1987-142 PROTON_01-Mar-2021-1-1.jdf		
Date	01 Mar 2021 09:54:29	Nucleus	1H
Solvent	CHLOROFORM-d	Number of Transients	16
Temperature (degree C)	20.600	Frequency (MHz)	399.7822
		Origin	JEOL ECZ400S Ca

¹H NMR (CHLOROFORM-d, 400 MHz) δ 7.2-7.3 (m, 26H), 6.94 (s, 1H), 6.80 (d, 1H, *J*=8.4 Hz), 5.2-5.3 (m, 2H), 4.9-5.2 (m, 9H), 4.6-4.7 (m, 6H), 4.5-4.5 (m, 1H), 4.2-4.4 (m, 4H), 4.1-4.2 (m, 1H), 3.9-4.0 (m, 2H), 3.5-3.6 (m, 1H), 3.3-3.4 (m, 4H), 3.26 (s, 2H), 3.17 (s, 3H), 2.15 (s, 1H), 1.7-1.8 (m, 2H), 1.3-1.4 (m, 2H), 1.2-1.3 (m, 8H), 0.85 (t, 3H, *J*=6.9 Hz)

Compound 5

Compound 5

WH15 Compd 15 C8

Item #

Batch # KS1987-142

File Name	\\sulfur\private\nmrdata\JEOL_2021\KS-1987-142\KS-1987-142 PHOSPHORUS 01-Mar-2021-1-1.jdf		
Date	01 Mar 2021 10:10:54	Nucleus	31P
Solvent	CHLOROFORM-d	Frequency (MHz)	161.8347
Temperature (degree C)	20.500	Number of Transients	16
		Origin	JEOL ECZ400S Ca

^{31}P NMR (CHLOROFORM-d, 162 MHz) δ -0.62 (s, 1P), -0.64 (s, 1P),
-6.01 (s, 1P), -6.15 (s, 1P)

Compound 6

Compound 6

Compound 6

putt-massey-500-1.991.fid

H1 standard parameters, BBFO probe. DEB-3065-C in CD3OD, 299K. Pos. 34.

Compound 7

Compound 7

putt-massey-500-1.993.fid
F19 standard parameters, BBFO probe. DEB-3-065-C in CD3OD, 299K. Pos. 34.

Compound 7

^{19}F NMR (470 MHz, MeOD) δ -67.58.

putt-massey-500-1.994.fid

P31 standard parameters, BBFO probe. DEB-3-065-C in CD3OD, 299K. Pps. 34.

Compound 7

^{31}P NMR (202 MHz, MeOD) δ 3.69, 2.71, -4.13.

Compound 7

27-May-2021

DEB-3-037-RP-F26-28-REDO

DEB-3-037-RP-F26-28-REDO

